

Promoting access to higher education for students with disabilities in rural contexts through open distance e-learning

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Abstract

Open Distance e-Learning (ODeL) institutions of higher learning are set to offer students alternative modes of tuition delivery, including students in deep-rural areas. Although a technology-driven approach to teaching and learning can bridge the gap created by geographical distance between educators and students, facilitate prompt feedback and provide remediation in advanced formats, this may pose unprecedented challenges for students with disabilities. The research focused on issues related to ODeL and its role in promoting access to higher education for students in isolated rural locations, specifically in the South African context. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews to establish the feelings and experiences of students with disabilities who live in deep-rural areas and who are enrolled with ODeL institutions of higher learning. The main finding was that higher education institutions that offer an ODeL mode of tuition should be decentralised by establishing e-learning centres in rural communities. The study objective was to reveal the challenges encountered by students with disabilities in their attempt to access the ODeL mode of learning, and the strategies to promote access to higher education through technological advancements. The study aims to promote a common understanding of disabilities and barriers to learning through ODeL in the context of rural areas.

Key terms: *access, disabilities, e-learning, higher education, institutions of higher learning, open distance, rural areas*

1. Introduction and background

In recent years, many institutions of higher learning have transcended from a traditional face-to-face mode of curriculum delivery to online e-learning (Mpungose 2020) – in South Africa and internationally. This transition was complicated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which led to lockdowns and restrictions in terms of physical access to most of the available economic and educational facilities. This situation resulted in the infusion of transformed curricula and a complete paradigm shift from teaching in traditional ways to implementing more advanced, technology-driven teaching and learning modalities. “Integrating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education is not only about having computer class, or teaching learners about the basic use of information technology, [but it] is about exploiting valuable services that ICT can offer to improve the pedagogy in education” (Makgati and Awolusi 2019, 50). Technology integration implies the use of technological apparatus that can offer students (including those in rural areas) equal access to tools that can be incorporated into online teaching and learning activities.

Despite ODeL being regarded as a suitable channel through which most students can access higher education, it remains a challenge for many students in remote rural areas who are living with disabilities. This article highlights the transactional gap that exists between students with disabilities and their online e-tutors – due to geographical location and other factors affecting their access to ODeL teaching and learning. Online learning or e-learning requires internet access, which may pose a learning barrier for students whose places of residence are in deep-rural locations (Mpungose 2020). Based on this background, the article endeavours to elucidate the disparities between institutions of higher learning that offer tuition through ODeL and challenges encountered by their registered students who have various disabilities. The study also focused on ways that ODeL can support students in rural contexts to gain access to and benefit from the programmes offered by institutions of higher learning. In light of this, the importance of ODeL cannot be underestimated; however, more research needs to be done on how to curb the discrepancies between ODeL mode of curriculum delivery and ease of access for students with disabilities, specifically those in far-off areas with poor infrastructure. This study therefore sought to answer the following questions:

- 1) What is the role of ODeL in higher education for students with disabilities in rural contexts?

- 2) How can rurality and socio-economic conditions affect students with disabilities in accessing education through ODeL?
- 3) What challenges do students with diverse disabilities face when accessing higher education through ODeL?

Owing to advancements in technology and the 4th industrial revolution (IR), institutions of higher learning have been vastly exploring methods of tuition delivery that may overcome challenges of distance, hence the shift from the traditional face-to-face mode of offering tuition to ODeL (Chandra 2019). As such, e-learning has become a preferred mode of tuition delivery as it provides a platform and valuable opportunities for students to engage in research. Institutions of higher learning are obliged to comply with current 4th IR requirements to develop and teach material online, which have affected the content that is taught and the mode of delivery, as well as the quality of the courses offered (Andrade et al. 2020). This article argues that despite the challenges faced by students with disabilities to access the ODeL mode of instruction, there is a continuous need for educational transformation across the globe to keep up with technological advancements. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an integral part of all levels of education and many institutions of higher learning have therefore adopted OdeL as an alternative mode of tuition delivery (Fidalgo et al. 2020).

2. Transactional distance theory (Tdt)

The Transactional Distance Theory (Moore 1973) focuses on making sense of the psychological and communication gaps that prevail (in the context of this study) between the students and their e-tutors or lecturers, due to physical or psychological separation, which is termed as "transactional distance." The physical separation between students and their e-tutors creates considerable distance between them, as compared to the traditional instructor-centred mode of tuition in conventional institutions of higher learning (Abuhassna and Alnawajha 2023). The proponents of TDT (Abuhassna and Alnawajha 2023) allude that transactional distance (TD) between the students and their lecturers may likely become more troublesome, resulting in a sense of isolation, less motivation, and lack of engagement for students. TDT comprises key components such as dialogue, structure, learner autonomy, learner-teacher interaction, and structure-dialogue dialectic (Moore 1973). For this study, the researchers have focused on how the variables of *dialogue* and *structure* determine transactional distance.

Figure 1. Moore's Theory of Transactional Distance

Daniel Bornt (2011).

As Moore et al. (2007) explain, Transactional Distance Theory (TDT) postulates that effective learning occurs through meaningful dialogue between learners and instructors. This dialogue assumes various forms, including written communication, discussions, feedback, and interaction within learning environments. Dialogical interaction helps to bridge the transactional distance by fostering engagement, understanding, and collaboration (Achuthan et al. 2024). In the context of this article, meaningful dialogue implies ensuring that students with various disabilities in rural areas are engaged in online teaching and learning activities and that they collaborate with their e-tutors and peers in an online learning environment.

Transactional Distance Theory emphasises the importance of structured learning environments in reducing transactional distance. Clear organisation, well-defined goals, structured activities, and guidelines for interaction help learners to navigate the learning process more effectively. Structured environments provide a framework for meaningful dialogue and promote active engagement in learning activities (Kotzé 2020). To provide appropriate opportunities for distance learning, provision should be made for appropriately structured learning material which ensures reduction of transactional distance by making use of dialogical interactions such as teleconferences, discussion forums, interactive multimedia content, online polls and surveys, and others (Moore 1997, 3).

3. Methodology of the study

3.1 The research design

The study employed a qualitative research design, which involved collecting the data using semi-structured interviews. Qualitative research enables the researcher to understand phenomena under investigation and to generate meaning, purpose and actual opinions and experiences of participants in specific contexts (Asenahabi 2020). Semi-structured interviews were mostly preferred because they are often open-ended, allowing for flexibility (George 2022).

3.2 Participant selection

Eight (n=8) participants were purposively sampled. The participants were students enrolled in a South African ODeL institution of higher learning. Purposive sampling refers to non-probability sampling techniques that involve the selection of units based on their common characteristics (Nikolopoulou 2022). Another criterion targeted in purposive sampling was to select students with various disabilities such as visual, auditory and mobility difficulties who live in rural areas in the peripheral landscapes of Polokwane in Limpopo Province. The researchers had to further use snowball sampling to allow the first few participants who meet the criteria to connect with other students they know, who have disabilities and who are registered with an ODeL institution of higher learning. In snowball sampling, a few currently selected participants who have agreed to be involved in the study help to recruit future subjects for a study (Simkus 2023).

4. Data analysis and findings

Qualitative content analysis was used to analyse the data that was collected through semi-structured interviews. Qualitative content analysis was used to identify patterns, themes, and meanings within the data. Shava et al. (2021, 554) describe it as “a research method for the subjective interpretation of the content of data through the systematic classification process of coding and identifying themes or patterns”.

Table 1. Themes that emerged from the analysed data

Predetermined themes from research questions	Sub-themes
1. The role of ODeL in higher education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geographical locations - Flexibility in learning
2. Effects of rurality and socio-economic condition on access to ODeL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gadgets for online learning - Students' financial statuses - Network and connectivity challenges - Unemployment and lack of resources - Lack of social interaction and peer support
3. Diverse disabilities and access to ODeL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of facilities - Need for assistive technology - Communication barriers - Procurement of assistive devices - Access to internet cafés

Table 1 illustrates the data that was analysed in tandem with the main themes that were predetermined from the research questions, implying that data coding was done deductively. Sub-themes have emerged from the verbatim data transcripts that were coded to reveal the participants' feelings and experiences regarding access to higher education through ODeL, with special reference to the predetermined main themes. The findings of the study are presented in the subsequent sections.

4.1 The role of ODeL in higher education

Two participants (Participant 3 and Participant 5) indicated that ODeL plays an important role in providing education for students whilst they are in the comfort of their homes. They reiterated that students could access online education in institutions of higher learning without geographical barriers – thus, ease of access for students (those with and those without disabilities). The following verbal quotes indicate what the participants have said:

“ODeL helps learners or student to study at [sic] the comfort of their homes. They can study wherever they are, wherever they are comfortable.” (Participant 3).

“I think it's very helpful or for those with disabilities, because they can study wherever they are, and they are not limited by geographical places.” (Participant 5).

It was further noted that ODeL provides flexibility in teaching and learning as the students work in their own places and that e-learning is accessible by anyone at any time. It is just a

matter of clicking and providing login details – and teaching and learning take place. See the verbatim quote below:

“I think open distance e-learning is helpful depending on the type of disability of the students. Well, firstly e-learning enables a lot of flexibility to be available anywhere at any time in the world. So, if students with disabilities have access to a computer or maybe electronic device, they will be sorted.” (Participant 1).

4.2 Effects of rurality and socio-economic conditions on access to ODeL

Rural areas vary according to regions, economic activities, population distribution, infrastructure and many other factors. In the context of this article, rurality refers to the critical lower socio-economic conditions that prevent students from having access to ODeL tuition and learning. The current study focused mainly on access to higher education for students with disabilities in deep-rural areas of the Limpopo Province in South Africa.

When asked about the effects of rurality and its socio-economic conditions on access to higher education through ODeL, the participants shared their feelings and experiences. Most of the participants were not happy about network and connectivity issues, which in most cases place them at a disadvantage, especially in online engagements such as Microsoft Teams meetings and discussions, participating in Forum activities and so forth. Submission of online activities are in many instances interrupted by poor connectivity, exacerbated by a lack of proper gadgets for online engagement. The following direct quotes revealed the feelings and experiences of participants:

“Most of the people who live in rural areas don't have access to Internet and some don't even have access to computers or laptops. We have network problems because there aren't many network towers. You might experience network issues if you are in like deeper areas within mountains and restrictions to the network. It is a challenge, especially when it comes to Teams meetings and discussion forums” (Participants 2, 4 and 7).

Some of the participants have indicated poor socio-economic conditions in deep-rural areas – such as low financial backgrounds, unemployment and lack of social interaction and peer support, especially for students with disabilities. Below is what the participants have said.

“Most of the people in rural areas are not working, that's why there is lack of resources to assist students with disabilities to be able to study freely.” (Participant 6).

“You may find that people are struggling to connect and partner with other people, their peers in the university. So, if they can't access higher education because their disabilities are limiting them, it's a serious problem.” (Participant 8)

4.3. Diverse disabilities and access to ODeL

When asked about students in rural areas with various disabilities and their access to ODeL, all eight participants bemoaned their frustrations in terms of proper facilities and assistive devices that will enable them to participate effectively in online teaching and learning. The excerpts below reflect some of the feelings and opinions of participants:

“Students with visual impairments may find it difficult to learn through the screen, and the fact that they are in rural areas where there is lack of facilities, they find it challenging to study using the computer screen.” (Participant 5).

“I think that students who cannot hear, are much better than [sic] those who cannot see. The only challenge that they may face is having projections that can display information for them as well as Sign Language interpreters as they are staying in rural areas. Another thing is that they may not have access to funds to buy that equipment or to have access to those facilities.” (Participant 1).

“Hearing aids are very expensive to get especially in rural areas. We normally wait for a long time, at least 10 years for the public hospital to provide us with hearing aids.” (Participant 4).

Some of the participants have indicated that students with mobility difficulties are better off than others who have visual and auditory impairments. Two of the participants (Participants 3 and 7) have reiterated that if students with mobility difficulties had the right gadgets at home, they wouldn't be facing much difficulty, especially because open distance e-learning accommodates their study needs. The participants have further indicated that the only challenge is with access to proper internet connections and the students with mobility difficulties would

then have to go to the internet cafés, which one can hardly find in remote areas. The verbatim quotes below indicate what the participants have said:

“If a person is using a wheelchair, even the issue of transportation is a problem because you have to request for a transport [sic] to take you from your home to the place where there is connectivity.” (Participant 3).

“If I don't have a device in my house and I need to go to an Internet café to do my assignment, the challenge is that I don't have anybody who can take me there. Then I feel stressed because I won't be able to submit my assignment. Worse than this, I can't get in the public transport because nobody can accommodate me and my wheelchair in a public taxi.” (Participant 8).

5. Discussion

The findings from the qualitative content analysis under the theme: *The role of ODeL in higher education* suggest that ODeL provides opportunities for students with disabilities to learn in the comfort of their homes, without restrictions that may emanate from geographical locations. In rural areas with limited physical access to institutions of higher learning, ODeL bridges the gap by allowing students with disabilities to learn remotely. These sentiments are shared by Haleem et al. (2022, 277) when they attest that e-learning systems are being made compatible with new smart devices such as phones and tablets which can be used for ease of access and faster uptake of digital learning. According to the Transactional Distance Theory (TDT) that was adopted to inform the search findings in this study, dialogical interactions can be incorporated into distance learning environments. These would enable the instructors (e-tutors and lecturers) to create more interactive, engaging, and collaborative learning experiences that could help reduce transactional distance.

The analysed data on the role of ODeL in higher education further revealed flexibility in online teaching and learning. Flexibility in distance education is a critical element in individualising the learning process as it covers all students' activities which include attending classes and comprises flexible learning in terms of learning pace and time (Mpungose 2020; Armstrong-Mensah et al. 2020). As Maphosa and Bhebhe (2020), Turan et al. (2022) and Müller et al.

(2023) explained, students become more autonomous in their learning processes because ODeL offers them a high level of flexibility in terms of technology, learning resources and tuition.

The analysis of data on the theme: *Effects of rurality and socio-economic conditions on access to ODeL* showed that students with disabilities living in far-off rural areas of South Africa are adversely affected by their socio-economic background. In particular, the study revealed poor connectivity, a lack of proper gadgets to enable students with disabilities to access ODeL, and low financial statuses due to insufficient employment opportunities. Nazir and Khan (2021) bemoaned that the issue of poor connectivity in deep-rural locations, coupled with a lack of employment opportunities, greatly hampers access to open distance e-learning for residents in these areas. For students with disabilities who live in deep-rural areas, access to higher education and ODeL is often determined by their perceptions about life in general, which may in turn be fuelled by their environmental and socio-economic conditions. According to Ali et al. (2023), limitations in terms of resources and facilities as well as parental encouragement and support (owing to socio-cultural reasons), high unemployment rates that result in poverty, and inadequate access to finance within families will have direct and indirect effects on rural students' ability to access higher education.

It follows that lower socio-economic status in remote areas may contribute to these students' inability to access higher education, which can furthermore be linked to the historical and colonial systems of education that may still be prevailing in many African countries. According to News24 (2018-04-18 10, 21), the apartheid system of education in South Africa, specifically "Bantu Education", has similarly left a legacy that continues to haunt South Africans. Other factors such as a lack of funding and relevant resources may also hinder students with disabilities in rural areas from gaining successful access to ODeL. A study conducted by Chandra (2019) in India revealed that, although education can contribute to improving socio-economic status and developing rural areas, some people will remain trapped in poverty.

The TDT interconnects with rurality and socio-economic conditions when it comes to factors such as access to resources, dialogue and communication barriers, as well as learner or student autonomy. Transactional distance in the context of rurality and socio-economic conditions for students' access to ODeL therefore implies pedagogical and psychological distance – a gap that exists between students and their e-tutors. This article argues that due to rurality and its accompanying socio-economic conditions, the psychological and communication space

between students with disabilities and their e-tutors in a virtual learning environment turns into a transactional distance. Therefore, rural areas with poor connectivity and limited access to educational resources tend to have greater transactional distance – due to barriers in communication and interaction. The above conditions thus impede ODeL, which is meant to be conducted beyond physical space and time and is aided by technology and educational tools that allow students and instructors to interact either synchronously or asynchronously (Crawford and McKenzi 2023; Abuhassna and Alnawajha 2023). Synchronous instruction implies that e-tutors/lecturers and students meet (usually online) for a session at a predetermined time, whereas asynchronous instruction refers to the situation where e-tutors and students do not have synchronous sessions, but students have access to course content through the internet at any time they deem it necessary (Fidalgo et al. 2020).

The results of the qualitative content analysis in terms of *diverse disabilities and access to ODeL* showed that students with differing disabilities are not equally affected by their geographical locations or rural areas in the context of this article. The study revealed a lack of the necessary infrastructure to support accessible technology and internet use, which pose significant barriers to online learning for students with disabilities. Students with, for example, visual impairments need specialised assistive technology such as compatible screen readers, accessible multimedia content and alternative text for images. Mishra (2023) agrees that individuals with visual impairments require assistive technologies such as screen readers, braille displays and text-to-speech software to enhance their access to library resources. Students with visual impairments in rural areas may experience difficulties accessing ODeL coupled with social isolation. Their state of disability may inhibit them from interacting with peers in an online learning environment and in their community, which in turn will have a negative effect on their overall educational experience.

The findings of this study further disclosed that students with auditory impairments find it difficult to access ODeL in higher education, but not in the same manner as students with visual impairments do. It was found that students with auditory impairments who live in rural areas find it difficult to communicate with their e-tutors and the people around them because of their usage of Sign Language. Many people in deep-rural areas are not yet conversant with Sign Language because in some communities' deaf people are still denied the use of Sign Language (Gournaris 2019, 3). In the same vein, Zenda (2023) attests that although South Africa is making some progress in the recognition of Sign Language as an official language, acknowledgement of, training in, and standards for sign language interpretation remain varied

and insufficient in countries across the continent (Zimbabwe, Kenya and Ghana), where Sign Language is officially recognised. It was further revealed that students with auditory impairments are facing challenges with regard to the procurement of hearing aids and the long waiting period in case such assistive devices are supposed to be provided by rural public hospitals. This was reported to have adverse effects on such students' progress in online learning or access to ODeL. Without the hearing aid, the affected student is unable to participate in an online discussion that takes place via Microsoft Teams or other channels. The challenge would be aggravated by a lack of Sign Language instructions in an online activity or absence of a Sign Language interpreter during onscreen presentations and oral discussions.

Furthermore, the study findings revealed that students with mobility disabilities are more likely to face challenges regarding access to internet cafés in times of poor connectivity in their rural vicinities. Boarding public transport whilst using a wheelchair was reported to be one of the major challenges for students with mobility difficulties. This finding is affirmed by Mwaka et al. (2024) stating that persons with physical or mobility difficulties who are using manual wheelchairs may have difficulty boarding the bus in the absence of a ramp. Access to public transport for individuals with physical disabilities is crucial for their independence and their participation/inclusion in education, ODeL, employment and healthcare.

6. Recommendations

Drawing from the findings and the Transactional Distance Theory that served as the driving force behind this study, it is recommended that universities and institutions of higher learning should ensure decentralisation of ODeL activities by establishing e-learning centres which are fortified with internet facilities in rural communities. This way, access to higher education will be realised for students with disabilities in rural contexts. ODeL institutions of higher learning should conduct research in rural communities to establish whether there are students with disabilities who are registered with such institutions, with the purpose of providing the necessary support to them. The recommended support can involve providing students with the assistive technology devices relevant to their disabilities to enable them to have access to ODeL learning environments. Rural communities also need to be educated or enlightened about offering support to persons with disabilities. Lastly, students with various disabilities who are enrolled at any institution of higher learning should be supported financially, either through bursaries or reasonable government-aided financial support that would enable them to access higher education, specifically ODeL mode of pedagogical impartation. It is recommended that the findings of this study should serve as a springboard for further research on the same topic.

7. Conclusion

The study investigated strategies to use ODeL to promote access to higher education for students with disabilities in rural contexts. To achieve the said goal, the study attempted to answer the research questions pertaining to the role of ODeL in higher education, rurality and its socio-economic effects on students with disabilities who are enrolled in ODeL institutions of higher learning, and the impact of various disabilities on students' access to ODeL in rural settings. It was generally recommended that institutions of higher learning should take charge of the predicaments faced by students with disabilities who live in rural areas – so that they too can have access to ODeL.

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